

Trees of Odisha state, India: Diversity and Conservation

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A tree is a perennial, woody plant typically having a single main stem or trunk covered with bark, supporting branches and leaves. According to the Global Tree Assessment (GTA), a tree is defined as a woody plant usually with a single stem growing to a height of at least two metres, or if multi-stemmed, having at least one vertical stem five centimetres in diameter at breast height (Kozłowski and Song, 2022). They are the main building blocks of forest ecosystems, which cover about 31% of the earth's land area. Trees also change the environments where they grow, making them important “**ecosystem engineers**”. They provide many benefits such as cleaning water, preventing soil erosion, reducing the risk of floods, storing carbon, cooling the air, and improving air quality (Stanturf and Mansourian, 2020). Many studies show that planting and protecting trees can help in the fight against climate change. Odisha state, located on the eastern coast of India, is renowned for its rich natural heritage and diverse ecosystems ranging from coastal plains and river basins to dense forests and hills. The state is home to a significant portion of India's forest cover, comprising around 32% of its geographical area (Reddy et al., 2013). Odisha's varied topography, climate, and soil types contribute to the high diversity of tree species found across its landscapes. Notable species include *Shorea robusta* (Sal), *Tectona grandis* (Saguan), *Diospyros melanoxylon* (Kendu), *Terminalia arjuna* (Arjuna), *Madhuca indica* (Mahula), *Butea monosperma* (Palash), and various species of *Ficus*. These trees not only form the backbone of Odisha's Forest ecosystems but also play a crucial role in supporting tribal livelihoods, maintaining soil fertility, regulating water cycles, and providing habitat to a variety of wildlife, including elephants, leopards, and endemic birds. Many tribal communities in Odisha depend heavily on forest resources for food, medicine, fuelwood, and cultural practices. Odisha, with its rich ecological diversity and extensive forest cover, has been the subject of numerous floristic studies over the years, many of which have significantly contributed to our understanding of its tree diversity. One of the earliest and most comprehensive works was by H. H. Haines, entitled “*The Botany of Bihar and Orissa*” (1921–1925), which laid the foundation for botanical research in the region with 386 tree species. Later, Orissa Forest Development Corporation Ltd., Bhubaneswar & Regional Research Laboratory, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, published a landmark four-volume work titled “*The Flora of Orissa*” (1994–1996) by HO Saxena and M. Brahmam, documenting 475 species of trees. Nayak, Kar and Mandal (2014) recorded 240 tree species from Similipal Biosphere Reserve, Odisha, and recorded a new generic record for tree diversity of

Odisha *Sloanea sterculiacea* (Elaeocarpaceae). Kar T, Khora SS and Mandal KK (2019), were recorded 140 tree species in the “*Floral Diversity of Bonai*”. Kumar et al. (2022) documented 138 tree species in the book entitled “*Floral Diversity Koira and Barsuan Ranges of Bonai Forest Division, Odisha*”. State is also home of many threatened tree species like *Alphonsea lutea* (Roxb.) Hook. f. & Thoms., *Lasiococca comberi* Haines, *Siphonodon celastrineus* Griff., *Cocculus laurifolius* DC., *Searsia paniculata* (Wall. ex G. Don) Moffett, *Syzygium schmidii* Rathakr. & N. C. Nair, *Cassipourea ceylanica* (Gardn.) Alston, *Prunus pygeoides* Koehne, *Sonneratia griffithii* Kurz, *Eriolaena hookeriana* Wight & Arn. var. *viridis* Haines, *Tritaxis glabella* (Thw.) R. Y. Yu & Welzen, *Garcinia xanthochymus* Hook. f. ex T. Anders., and *Litsea glutinosa* (Lour.) Robins. Odisha's rich biodiversity and extensive forest cover have led to numerous conservation initiatives. The state government has emphasized the importance of protecting its ecological wealth, including forests, wetlands, and coastal regions. Many organizations and researchers are continue working together to document and preserve Odisha's tree diversity.

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